

CROSS DOMAIN SENTIMENT CLASSIFICATION USING CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORK

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Abstract

This paper proposes using most similar domain to target domain as source domain among available domains for training the classifier. Training a classifier for polarity detection when labeled data is not available, poses a challenge. Annotating data manually is a labor intensive and costly process. Also when there are many different domains present, it is not practical to create a classifier for every domain. Thus cross domain sentiment classification is highly desirable to reduce the domain dependency and cost of annotating data manually. A major concern in existing solutions for cross domain sentiment classification is that if source domain varies significantly from the target domain, classifier learned may not perform well and may show a very degraded accuracy. To overcome this threat, present research proposes the use of similarity measure, which will choose the most similar source domain to the target domain from among the available domains. Thus obtained source domain will be use for training the deep learning neural network. Past researches have used linear classifier like SVM, kNN , Naive Bayes etc. This paper proposes using convolutional neural network, a non-linear classifier which can fit the data more easily.

1 Introduction

As more people are expressing themselves online, the need arises to classify their views and opinions

according to the polarity which helps other potential customers and manufacturers in decision making. Sentiment analysis on reviews generated by the users on different products is used to detect the polarity of review. Sentiment analysis is the process of automatically detecting whether a text is positive or negative[1]. Traditional supervised machine learning approaches have shown promising results[2]. These studies considered that both the training data and test data are from the same domain and identically distributed. But in real case scenario it is not always possible to have sufficient labeled data for training. Thus need arises to train the domain having less data with the domain having sufficient labeled data. If the distribution of training data and testing data are significantly different than the performance of the classifier may be reduced. Thus the need arises to first select the source domain which is most similar to the target domain in the distribution, for training the classifier.

To address the problem of cross domain sentiment analysis[3]proposed structural correspondence learning(SCL) approach for domain adaption. The SCL finds correspondences among different features from both source and target domain using the correlations with pivot features and non-pivot features.Pivot features are those features which occur in both domains and behave in the same way in both domains. [4] used sentiment sensitive thesaurus for cross-domain sentiment classifier. Labeled data from multiple source domains and unlabeled data from both the source

domain and target domain is used to create sentiment sensitive thesaurus. Thesaurus is used to expand feature vectors during training and testing of binary classifier.[5]proposed an active learning approach for cross domain sentiment classification by leveraging QBC-based sample selection and combination-based classifier classification. These conventional approaches must extract customized features from the text and then feed the features into a shallow classifier such as SVM. Shallow architecture has proven itself in solving many simple or well constrained problems, but their limited architecture and representation can cause difficulties when dealing with more complicated real world applications. These processes are task specific. The classifiers are designed according to the features of a particular domain. It requires cost, time, expertise and feature engineering for designing classifier. That is why it become difficult creating a classifier for every classification task.

In broader family of machine learning methods, there is a member "deep learning" method, which works in contrast of task specific algorithms. Deep Learning uses a sequence of layers of non linear processing units for feature extraction[6][7]. It works on the same principal on which human brain mechanism works. Each successive layer uses the output from the previous layer as input. It is based on the learning of multiple levels of features of the data. Higher level features are derived from lower level features to form a hierarchical representation.

This paper proposes to use the domain which is most similar to target domain out of the available domains for training the classifier. In addition convolutional neural network classifier will be used to leverage the capability of deep learning.

2 Proposed Work

The proposed work will use a source domain for training the model for classification of reviews

from the target domain. In the first step, domain similarity of all the available source domains with the target domain will be calculated and most similar source domain will be selected. The assumption is that similar domains usually share more common terms than dissimilar domains. For example, Mobile phone and Laptop domains share many common words like screen, battery, memory etc., while domains like mobile phone and books are significantly different.

This research will use Jensen Shannon Divergence for measuring the distance between two domains. Jensen Shannon Divergence has been proven to outperform other similarity metrics[8]. Jensen Shannon Divergence which provides symmetric distance metric is as follows:

$$JSD(X||Y) = \frac{1}{2}KL(X||A) + \frac{1}{2}KL(Y||A)$$

where $A = \frac{1}{2}(X + Y)$.

Jensen Shannon Divergence will help in selecting the most similar source domain to the target domain.

In the next step available labeled data from that source domain will be cleaned. Different sub steps will be conducted for cleaning data for training the classifier, like tokens will be split on white space, all punctuations will be removed from the words, all the words that are not purely comprised of alphabetical characters will be removed, all known stop words will be removed.

Next step will train the classifier using cleaned data from source domain to classify the reviews from target domain. The proposed work will use convolutional neural network as classifier, which will be trained on the selected source domain. A convolutional neural network can learn the internal structure of data. The input review from the target domain will be converted into vector form using word embeddings. Then the convolutional neural layers will extract the features from target review. The polarity of review is then determined by softmax classifier.

The performance of the model will be determined using the following measures:

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + FN + TN + FP}$$

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

$$Recall = \frac{P}{TP + FN}$$

where TP, TN, FP and FN are true positive, true negative, false positive and false negative respectively.

Figure 1: Steps for cross-domain sentiment classification

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